

Integration of analytical, empirical, and numerical methods in analyzing support requirements for tunneling in weak rock

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Abstract

This paper presents the results of the integration of analytical, empirical, and numerical methods in analyzing the support requirements needed to stabilize a hypothetical circular tunnel in a weak rock mass. First, the convergence-confinement method is used as the analytical method to determine the required support pressure to control tunnel displacement. Rock mass classification systems (RMR and Q) are used as the empirical method to evaluate the quality and strength of the rock masses and to obtain the recommended support systems. Finally, two-dimensional plane strain and axisymmetric models in the computer program FLAC are used as the numerical method to evaluate the ground behavior and the performance of the recommended support systems. Results show that after the suggested support system is installed, the extent of deformation and the thickness of the plastic radius around the tunnel decreases significantly. This result indicates that the integration of the analytical, empirical, and numerical methods in designing tunnel support is recommended for a reliable support design. Simplicity in the analytical and analytical methods may lead to the first estimate of ground behavior, while the numerical method can be used to verify the performance of the excavated ground and of the support system suggested by the empirical method.

1. Introduction

When tunneling through a weak rock mass, determining tunnel support requirements is not only a nontrivial task but also an iterative process. The current practice in the design of tunnel reinforcement and supports depends upon the rock mass classification used and the experience of the tunnel designers. This paper presents a simple yet practical approach to integrate analytical, empirical, and numerical methods in analyzing the support requirements to stabilize tunnel in a weak rock mass. The method is demonstrated using a hypothetical circular tunnel but is expected to be applicable to actual construction. It is envisioned that the simplicity in the analytical and empirical methods may lead to the first estimate of ground behavior, while the numerical method can be used to verify the performance of the excavated ground and of the support system suggested by the empirical method.

For the case study in this paper, a circular tunnel with a radius of $R = 5$ m is excavated in a weak homogenous and isotropic rock mass at a depth of $H = 260$ m from the surface. Circular tunnel is chosen to provide a direct comparison with the corresponding analytical solutions in terms of stress and deformation around the excavation. The conditions of the rock mass surrounding the tunnel are given in Table 1 to make a hypothetical rock mass quantified using the Q -system (Barton, 2002; Barton, Lien, & Lunde, 1974), which is one of the two most commonly used rock mass classification system for tunneling. The other is the Rock Mass Rating (RMR) developed by Bieniawski (1989), and correlations between the

two systems are available. The Q -system is chosen to represent the weak rock mass in this paper because after 40 years of its development with more than 2,000 cases of tunnels/caverns, it is still the most consistent and reliable rock mass classification that gives the best fit between rock quality, excavation dimensions, and support quantities (Barton & Grimstad, 2014). According to Table 1, the weak rock mass surrounding the tunnel has $Q = 0.2$ and $RMR = 45$, classified as a very poor rock mass and fair rock mass, respectively.

Table 1 Rock mass conditions surrounding the tunnel

Parameter	Symbol	Rating	Description
Rock Quality Designation	RQD	60	Fair rock mass with $RQD = 60\%$
Joint set number	J_n	12	Three joint sets plus random joints
Joint roughness number	J_r	1.5	Rough or irregular, planar joints
Joint alteration number	J_a	2	Slightly altered joint walls
Joint water reduction factor	J_w	0.66	Medium inflow or pressure
Stress Reduction Factor	SRF	5.0	High stress
Tunneling Quality Index	Q	0.50	Very poor rock mass
Normalized Q	Q_c	0.2	
Rock Mass Rating	RMR	45	Fair rock mass

In addition, the rock mass is assumed to have the density of $\rho = 2,700 \text{ kg/m}^3$, intact Young's modulus $E = 18,000 \text{ MPa}$, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$, and intact uniaxial compressive strength $\sigma_c = 50 \text{ MPa}$.

The Q -value, Q_c , and RMR in Table 1 are calculated using the following equations

$$Q = \frac{RQD}{J_n} \times \frac{J_r}{J_a} \times \frac{J_w}{SRF} \quad (1)$$

$$Q_c = Q \times \frac{\sigma_c}{100} \quad (2)$$

$$RMR = 15 \log Q + 50 \quad (3)$$

where RQD is the Rock Quality Designation defined as the % of competent drill-core sticks >100mm in length (Deere, 1968), J_n , J_r , J_a , J_w and SRF are the Q -system parameters as defined in Table 1. Note that Eq. (3) is the conversion between Q and RMR as proposed by Barton (1995).

2. Rock Mass Parameters

For the tunnel under study, the important rock mass parameters to be used in the analytical, empirical, and numerical methods are the deformation modulus E_{mass} , compressive strength $\sigma_{c_{mass}}$, cohesion c_{mass} , and friction angle of the rock mass ϕ_{mass} . In addition, the internal support pressure is needed to check whether plastic failure will occur, i.e., if the internal support pressure p_i is less than the critical support pressure p_{cr} , a zone of plastic failure or plastic zone will develop in the ground surrounding the tunnel (Carranza-Torres & Fairhurst, 2000). For the ground conditions defined in Table 1, the calculated rock mass parameters and internal support pressure suggested by several researchers are given in Table 2. According to Table 2, the average calculated E_{mass} , $\sigma_{c_{mass}}$, c_{mass} , ϕ_{mass} , and p_i are 7,753 MPa, 10.4 MPa, 0.5 MPa, 26.3°, and 0.11 MPa, respectively. These values will be used as the input parameters in the analytical and numerical models to evaluate the stress and deformation behavior of the tunnel.

3. Methodology

For the analytical method, the so-called convergence-confinement method (CCM) is used to evaluate displacement behavior of the tunnel and to determine the required support pressure to control the convergence. The CCM consists of the ground reaction curve (GRC), the support reaction curve (SRC), and the longitudinal displacement curve (LDP). The GRC represents the relationship between the increasing radial displacement of the tunnel u_r and the decreasing internal support pressure p_i . The relationship is analytically defined by Duncan Fama (1993) as:

$$u_r = \frac{R(1+\nu)}{E} \left[2(1-\nu)(\sigma_o - p_{cr}) \left(\frac{R_p}{R} \right) - (1-2\nu)(\sigma_o - p_i) \right] \quad (4)$$

where p_{cr} is the critical support pressure defined as $p_{cr} = \frac{2\sigma_o - \sigma_{cm}}{1+k}$, σ_o is the in situ stress defined as $\sigma_o = \rho g H$, k is the coefficient of active earth pressure defined as $k = \frac{1+\sin\phi_{mass}}{1-\sin\phi_{mass}}$, R_p is the radius of plastic zone defined

as $R_p = R \left[\frac{2(\sigma_o(k-1) + \sigma_{cm})}{(1+k)(k-1)p_i + \sigma_{cm}} \right]^{\frac{1}{(k-1)}}$ where σ_{cm} is the analytical rock mass compressive strength defined as $\sigma_{cm} = \frac{2c_{mass} \cos\phi_{mass}}{1-\sin\phi_{mass}}$.

Table 2 Summary of the rock mass properties.

Literature	E_{mass} (MPa)	σ_{cmass} (MPa)	c_{mass} (MPa)	ϕ_{mass} (°)	p_i (MPa)	Equation
Serafim and Pereira (1983)	7,682					$E_{mass} = 10^{\left(\frac{RMR-10}{40}\right)}$
Mitri et al. (1994)	7,752					$E_{mass} = E \left[0.5 \left(1 - \left\{ \cos \pi \frac{RMR}{100} \right\} \right) \right]$
Read et al. (1999)	9,369					$E_{mass} = 0.1 \left(\frac{RMR}{10} \right)^3$
Barton (1996)	6,279					$E_{mass} = 10Q_c^{\frac{1}{3}}$
Barton (2002)	7,682					$E_{mass} = 10^{(15 \log Q + 40)/40}$
Singh et al. (1997)		15.0				$\sigma_{cmass} = 7\gamma Q^{1/3}$
Trueman (1998)		7.6				$\sigma_{cmass} = 0.5 \exp^{0.06 RMR}$
Barton (2000)		8.5				$\sigma_{cmass} = 5\gamma \left(Q \frac{\sigma_c}{100} \right)^{1/3}$
Barton (2002)			0.50	26.3		$c_{mass} = \frac{RQD}{J_n} \times \frac{1}{SRF} \times \frac{\sigma_c}{100}$ $\phi_{mass} = \tan^{-1} \left(J_r / J_a \times J_w \right)$
Barton et al. (1974)					0.09	$p_i = J_r / \left(20Q^{1/3} \right)$
Grimstad and Barton (1993)					0.13	$p_i = \left(0.2 / J_a \right) Q^{-1/3}$
Goel et al. (1995)					0.12	$p_i = \frac{(7.5B^{0.1} \times H^{0.5} - RMR)}{20RMR}$
Average	7,753	10.4	0.50	26.3	0.11	

The SRC represents the relationship between the increasing support pressure p_s and the increasing radial displacement of the support u_s . To develop SRC, the maximum support pressure p_s^{max} and the elastic stiffness K_s of each support member must be calculated. Analytical calculations of these parameters are presented in Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (2000). For shotcrete

$$p_s^{\max} = \frac{\sigma_{cc}}{2} \left[1 - \frac{(R-t_c)^2}{R^2} \right] \quad \text{and} \quad K_s = \frac{E_c}{(1+\nu_c)R} \frac{R^2 - (R-t_c)^2}{(1-2\nu_c)R^2 + (R-t_c)^2} \quad (5)$$

while for rockbolt

$$p_s^{\max} = \frac{T_{bf}}{s_c s_l} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{1}{K_s} = s_c s_l \left[\frac{4l}{\pi d_b^2 E_s} + Q_b \right] \quad (6)$$

where σ_{cc} is the σ_c of the shotcrete, t_c is the shotcrete thickness, E_c is the Young's modulus of the shotcrete, ν_c is the Poisson's ratio of the shotcrete, T_{bf} is the ultimate load of the rockbolt, s_c and s_l are the circumferential and longitudinal bolt spacing, respectively, l is the rockbolt length, E_s is the Young's modulus of the bolt, and Q_b is the deformation-load constant.

Lastly, the LDP represents the radial displacement occurring along the longitudinal axis of the unsupported tunnel. According to Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009), the LDP of a circular tunnel in an elasto-plastic rock mass is defined as

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = \frac{u_o}{u_{r,max}} \exp(x/R) \text{ for } x/R \leq 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{u_o}{u_{r,max}} \right) \exp(-3x/R) / (2R_p/R) \text{ for } x/R \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

where u_o is the radial displacement at the tunnel face defined as $\frac{u_o}{u_{r,max}} = \frac{1}{3} \exp(-0.15 R_p/R)$, $u_{r,max}$ is the maximum radial displacement from Eq. **Error! Reference source not found.** by setting $p_i = 0$, and x is the distance from the tunnel face.

For the empirical method, the recommended support systems are then obtained based on the Q value calculated in Eq. (1), as also summarized in Table 1. Assuming the tunnel is for a road tunnel, as shown in Fig. 1, the recommended support system is a combination of fiber-reinforced shotcrete with the thickness of $t_c = 15$ cm, with reinforced ribs of shotcrete and bolting with rockbolt length of $l = 3$ m and spacing of $s_c = 1.6$ m.

Fig. 1. Chart for recommending tunnel support based on the Q -system (Grimstad & Barton, 1993).

Finally, as the numerical method, two-dimensional plane strain and axisymmetric models of the tunnel are developed using the computer program Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua or FLAC (Itasca, 2011). The numerical models are developed to evaluate the ground behavior and the performance of the recommended support systems. Fig. 2 shows the two models that are built in FLAC. The plane strain model is used to develop numerical GRC and to analyze the performance of the support system while the axisymmetric model is used to develop numerical LDP.

4. Results

Fig. 3 presents the developed CCM method based on the integration of the analytical, empirical, and numerical methods explained in Section 3. The match between the analytical and numerical solutions from FLAC is satisfactory. From the LDP curve, it can be observed that if the combined support system (rockbolt + fiber-reinforced shotcrete) is installed at $\frac{1}{2} R$ from the face (rather immediately due to ground conditions), or after the tunnel has deformed 1.2 cm, the support and the ground would deform together and reach equilibrium at $p_i = 0.6$ MPa and $u_r = 1.3$ cm. With $p_s^{\max} = 1.2$ MPa, the recommended support from the Q -system has a factor of safety of 2.0, indicating a satisfactory recommendation and resulting in a stable opening. The satisfactory performance of the support system can also be seen in Fig. 4. When the tunnel is unsupported, the vertical deformation at the crown is about 2.6 cm (corresponding with GRC and LDP curves) with a plastic radius of 13 m. After the tunnel is supported, the vertical deformation at the crown is reduced to only 1.3 cm (corresponding to the equilibrium point between GRC and SRC in Fig. 3) with a reduced plastic radius of only 7 m, indicating a reduced overstressed region surrounding the tunnel.

Fig. 2. (a) Plane strain and (b) axisymmetric tunnel models in FLAC.

Fig. 3. The CCM results from the analytical and numerical methods.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the induced deformation and plastic zone radius between the unsupported and supported tunnel.

5. Conclusion

The paper has shown that determining the support requirements for tunneling through weak rock masses is not a trivial task but rather an iterative process. However, by integrating analytical, empirical, and numerical methods, a satisfactory support design can be achieved. Results from the FLAC model show that after the suggested support system is installed, the extent of vertical deformation and the thickness of the plastic radius around the tunnel decrease significantly. These outcomes would be different if the support was installed too early (too close to the tunnel face) or too late (too far from the tunnel face). The analytical GRC and LDP curves proved to be helpful in determining the appropriate time to install the support.

This paper reinforces that integrating the analytical, empirical, and numerical methods in designing tunnel support is recommended for a reliable support design. Simplicity in the analytical and empirical methods may lead to the first estimate of ground behavior, while the numerical method can be used to verify the performance of the excavated ground and of the support system suggested by the empirical method.

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